

ON ALPHA ALPHA OF GENERALIZED STAR CLOSED SETS IN TOPOLOGICAL SPACES

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this paper is to introduce a new class of sets called $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ - closed sets in topological spaces and to study their properties. Further, we define and study $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ - open sets $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ - continuity.

Key Words: $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ - closed sets, $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ - open sets, $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ continuous.

1. INTRODUCTION

In 1970, Levine [9] introduced the concept of generalized closed set in the topological spaces and a class of topological spaces called T1/2 spaces. Extensive research on generalizing closedness was done in recent years by many mathematicians. In 1990, S.P. Arya and T.M. Nour [2] define generalized semi-open sets, generalized semi-closed sets. In 1993 Maki H, Devi R and Balachandran K [21] introduced generalized alpha closed ($g\alpha$ -closed) sets. K.Meena and V.P.Anuja [36] made an analytical study and gave the concepts of Alpha ^ Generalized Closed Sets in Topological Spaces

In this paper, we introduce a new class of sets called alpha alpha of generalized star - closed sets (briefly $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ -closed sets) and we study their basic properties. We recall the following definitions, which will be used often throughout this paper.

2. PRELIMINARIES

Throughout this paper, X, Y, Z denote the topological spaces $(X, \tau), (Y, \sigma)$ and (Z, η) respectively, on which no separation axioms are assumed. A being a subset of a topological space (X, τ) , $cl(A)$, $int(A)$ denote the closure of A and interior of A respectively. Replace (X, τ) with X if there is no chance of confusion

Definition 2.1: A subset A of a space X is called

- (1) a pre-open set if $A \subseteq int(cl(A))$ and a pre-closed set if $cl(int(A)) \subseteq A$.
- (2) a semi-open set if $A \subseteq cl(int(A))$ and a semi-closed set if $int(cl(A)) \subseteq A$.
- (3) an α -open set if $A \subseteq int(cl(int(A)))$ and a α -closed set if $cl(int(cl(A))) \subseteq A$.
- (4) a semi-preopen set ($=\beta$ -open) if $A \subseteq cl(int(cl(A)))$ and a semi-pre closed set (β -closed) if $int(cl(int(A))) \subseteq A$.

The semi-closure (resp. α -closure) of a subset A of (X, τ) is denoted by $scl(A)$ (resp. $\alpha cl(A)$ and $spcl(A)$) and is the intersection of all semi-closed (resp. α -closed and semi-pre closed) sets containing A.

Definition 2.2: A subset A of X is called

1. a generalized closed (briefly g-closed) [9] set iff $cl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is open in X.

2. Strongly generalized closed (briefly g^* closed)[20] if $cl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is g -open in X
3. a regular open [18] set if $A = int(cl(A))$ and regular closed[18] set if $A = cl(int(A))$.
4. a semi generalized closed (briefly sg – closed)[4] if $scl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is Semiopen in X .
5. a generalized semi closed (briefly gs – closed)[2] if $scl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is open in X .
6. a generalized semi-pre closed (briefly gsp – closed)[5] if $spcl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is open in X .
7. a regular generalized closed (briefly rg – closed)[15] if $cl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is regular open in X .
8. a generalized preclosed (briefly gp – closed) [10]if $pcl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is open in X .
9. a generalized pre regular closed (briefly gpr – closed)[7] if $pcl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is regular open in X .
10. a weakly closed (briefly w – closed)[16] if $cl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is semiopen in X .
11. a regular weakly closed (briefly rw – closed)[3] if $cl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is regular semiopen in X .
12. a weakly generalized semi closed (briefly wg – closed) [13] if $cl(int(A)) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is open in X .
13. a regular weakly generalized semi closed (briefly rwg – closed)[13] if $cl(int(A)) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is regular open in X .
14. a regular generalized weakly semi closed (briefly rgw – closed)[17] if $cl(int(A)) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is regular semi-open in X .
15. a regular[^] generalized closed (r^g closed)[22] if $gcl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is regular open.
16. g^{\wedge} - closed set [23] if $cl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is semi-open in (X, τ) .
17. αg^{\wedge} - closed set [24] if $\alpha cl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is g^{\wedge} -open in (X, τ) .
18. αg^* - closed set [25] if $cl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is α -open in (X, τ) .
19. $s\alpha g^*$ - closed set [26] if $\alpha cl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is g^* -open in (X, τ) .
20. $wg\alpha$ -closed set [27] if $\alpha cl(int(A)) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is α -open in (X, τ) .
21. $w\alpha g$ -closed set [27] if $\alpha cl(int(A)) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is open in (X, τ) .
22. ψ -closed set [28] if $scl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is sg -open in (X, τ) .
23. ψg -closed set [29] if $\psi cl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is open in (X, τ) .
24. $g^* \psi$ -closed set [30] if $\psi cl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is g -open in (X, τ) .
25. ψg^{\wedge} - closed set [31] if $\psi cl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is g^{\wedge} -open in (X, τ) .
26. $\alpha \psi$ - closed set [32] if $\psi cl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is α -open in (X, τ) .
27. $g\alpha^*$ - closed set [25] if $cl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is α -open in (X, τ) .
28. αg - closed set [33] if $\alpha cl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is open in (X, τ) .
29. $g\alpha$ - closed set [21] if $cl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is α -open in (X, τ) .
30. r^g - closed set [35] if $gcl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is regular open in (X, τ) .
31. α^g - closed sets [36] if $gcl(A) \subset U$, whenever $A \subset U$ and U is α -open in X
32. $(gsp)^*$ closed sets [37] if $cl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is gsp -open.
33. π -open if A is the union of regular open sets and π -closed [38] if A is the intersection of regular closed sets.

34. $(g\alpha r)^*$ - closed set [39] if $cl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is $g\alpha r$ - open in X .

The complements of the above mentioned closed sets are their respective open sets.

Definition 2.3: A map $f: X \rightarrow Y$ is said to be

1. a continuous function [1] if $f^{-1}(V)$ is closed in X for every closed set V in Y .
2. a pre continuous [11] if $f^{-1}(V)$ is pre closed in X for every closed set V in Y .
3. a α -continuous function [34] if $f^{-1}(V)$ is α -closed in X for every closed set V in Y .
5. a gs -continuous [1] if $f^{-1}(V)$ is gs closed in X for every closed set V in Y .
6. a αg -continuous [7] if $f^{-1}(V)$ is αg - closed in X for every closed set V in Y .
7. a rwg -continuous [13] if $f^{-1}(V)$ is rwg - closed in X for every closed set V in Y .
8. a rgw -continuous [13] if $f^{-1}(V)$ is rgw - closed in X for every closed set V in Y .
9. a swg -continuous [13] if $f^{-1}(V)$ is swg - closed in X for every closed set V in Y .

3. Alpha Alpha of Generalized Star Closed Sets $(\alpha(\alpha g))^*$ - closed sets)

Definition 3.1: A subset A of (X, τ) is called a alpha alpha of generalized star closed (**briefly $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed**) if $\alpha cl(A) \subset U$, whenever $A \subset U$ and U is αg -open in X .

We denote the family of all $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed sets in space X by $\alpha(\alpha G)^*C(X)$.

Theorem 3.2: Every closed set of a topological space (X, τ) is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed set.

Proof: Let $A \subset X$ be a closed set and $A \subset U$ where U be αg -open. Since A is closed and every closed set is αg -closed, $\alpha cl(A) \subset cl(A) = A \subset U$. Hence A is an $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed set.

Remark 3.3: The converse of the above theorem need not be true as seen in the following example.

Example 3.4: Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$, $\tau = \{X, \phi, \{a, b\}\}$. Let $A = \{a, c\}$ then A is an $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed set but it is not a closed set.

Theorem 3.5: Every g^\wedge -closed set is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed.

Proof: Let A be a g^\wedge -closed set. Let $A \subset U$ where U is αg -open. Since every αg -open set is semi open and A is g^\wedge closed, $cl(A) \subset U$. Every closed set is αg -closed therefore $\alpha cl(A) \subset cl(A) \subset U$. Hence A is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed.

Remark 3.6: The converse of the above theorem need not be true as seen in the following example.

Example 3.7: Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$, $\tau = \{X, \phi, \{a\}, \{a, b\}\}$. Let $A = \{b\}$ then A is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed set but it is not a g^\wedge -closed set.

Theorem 3.8: Every δ - closed set is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ is closed.

Proof: Let A be δ - closed . Let $A \subset U$ and U be αg open. Since A is αg^* closed, $\delta cl(A) \subset U$. Every δ - closed set is αg -closed, then $\alpha cl(A) \subset \delta cl(A) \subset U$. Hence A is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed.

Remark 3.9: The converse of the above theorem need not be true as seen in the following example.

Example 3.10: Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\tau = \{X, \phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}\}$. Let $A = \{c\}$ then A is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ -closed set but it is not a δ -closed set.

Theorem 3.11: Every αg^* -closed set is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ -closed.

Let A be αg^* -closed in (X, τ) . Let $A \subset U$ where U is αg -open. Since A is αg^* -closed, $\text{cl}(A) \subset U$. Every closed set is αg -closed, then $\alpha \text{cl}(A) \subset \text{cl}(A) \subset U$. Hence A is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ -closed.

Remark 3.12: The converse of the above theorem need not be true as seen in the following example.

Example 3.13: Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\tau = \{X, \phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}\}$. Let $A = \{c\}$ then A is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ -closed set but it is not a αg^* -closed set.

Theorem 3.14: Every $(gsp)^*$ -closed set is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ -closed.

Let A be $(gsp)^*$ -closed in (X, τ) . Let $A \subset U$ where U is αg -open. Since A is $(gsp)^*$ -closed, $\text{cl}(A) \subset U$. Since every αg -open is gsp -open, then $\alpha \text{cl}(A) \subset \text{cl}(A) \subset U$. Hence A is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ -closed.

Remark 3.15: The converse of the above theorem need not be true as seen in the following example.

Example 3.16: Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$, $\tau = \{X, \phi, \{a\}, \{a, b\}\}$. Let $A = \{b\}$ then A is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ -closed set but it is not a $(gsp)^*$ -closed set.

Theorem 3.17: Every regular closed set is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ -closed.

Let A be regular closed in (X, τ) . Let $A \subseteq U$ where U is αg -open in X . Since A is regular closed, $\text{rcl}(A) = A \subseteq U$, then $\alpha \text{cl}(A) \subseteq \text{rcl}(A) \subseteq U$. Hence A is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ -closed.

Remark 3.18: The converse of the above theorem need not be true as seen in the following example.

Example 3.19: Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$, $\tau = \{X, \phi, \{a\}, \{a, b\}\}$. Let $A = \{c\}$ then A is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ -closed set but it is not a regular-closed set.

Theorem 3.20: Every π -closed set is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ -closed.

Let A be π -closed set in (X, τ) . Let $A \subseteq U$ where U is αg -open in X . Since A is π -closed, $\pi \text{cl}(A) = A \subseteq U$, then $\alpha \text{cl}(A) \subseteq \pi \text{cl}(A) \subseteq U$. Hence A is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ -closed.

Remark 3.21: The converse of the above theorem need not be true as seen in the following example.

Example 3.22: Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\tau = \{X, \phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}\}$. Let $A = \{d\}$ then A is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ -closed set but it is not a π -closed set.

Theorem 3.23: Every $(g\alpha r)^*$ -closed set is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ -closed.

Let A be $(g\alpha r)^*$ -closed set in (X, τ) . Let $A \subseteq U$ where U is αg -open in X . Since A is $(g\alpha r)^*$ -closed, $\text{cl}(A) = A \subseteq U$. Since every αg -open is $g\alpha r$ -open, then $\alpha \text{cl}(A) \subseteq \text{cl}(A) \subseteq U$. Hence A is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ -closed.

Remark 3.24: The converse of the above theorem need not be true as seen in the following example.

Example 3.25: Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\tau = \{X, \phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}\}$. Let $A = \{c\}$ then A is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ -closed set but it is not a $(g\alpha r)^*$ -closed set.

Example 3.26: Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\tau = \{X, \phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}\}$. Then

1. rg -closed $= \{X, \phi, \{c\}\{d\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}\}$
2. αg -closed $= \{X, \phi, \{c\}\{d\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}\}$
3. αg^{\wedge} -closed $= \{X, \phi, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}\}$
4. gar -closed $= \{X, \phi, \{c\}\{d\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}\}$
5. ψ -closed $= \{X, \phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}\}$
6. ψg^{\wedge} -closed $= \{X, \phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}\}$
7. $s\alpha g^*$ -closed $= \{X, \phi, \{c\}\{d\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}\}$
8. gp -closed $= \{X, \phi, \{c\}\{d\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}\}$
9. g^*p -closed $= \{X, \phi, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}\}$
10. $r^{\wedge}g$ -closed $= \{X, \phi, \{c\}\{d\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}\}$
11. g -closed $= \{X, \phi, \{d\}\{a, d\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}\}$
12. g^* -closed $= \{X, \phi, \{d\}\{a, d\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}\}$
13. $\alpha^{\wedge}g$ -closed $= \{X, \phi, \{d\}\{a, d\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}\}$
14. $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ -closed $= \{X, \phi, \{c\}, \{d\}\{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}\}$

Theorem 3.27:

1. Every $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ -closed set is rg -closed.
2. Every $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ -closed set is αg -closed.
3. Every $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ -closed set is αg^{\wedge} -closed.
4. Every $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ -closed set is gar -closed.
5. Every $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ -closed set is ψ -closed.
6. Every $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ -closed set is ψg^{\wedge} -closed.
7. Every $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ -closed set is $s\alpha g^*$ -closed.
8. Every $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ -closed set is gp -closed.
9. Every $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ -closed set is g^*p -closed.
10. Every $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ -closed set is $r^{\wedge}g$ -closed.

Proof: Straight forward.

Remark 3.28: The converse of the above theorem need not be true as seen in the following examples.

In Example 3.26, $A = \{a, b\}$, then A is rg -closed. $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ -closed set

In Example 3.26, $A = \{a, d\}$, then A is αg -closed but not $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ -closed set

In Example 3.26, $A = \{b, d\}$, then A is αg^{\wedge} -closed. but not $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ -closed set

In Example 3.26, $A = \{a, b\}$, then A is gar -closed but not $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ -closed set

In Example 3.26, $A = \{a\}$, then A is ψ -closed but not $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ -closed set

In Example 3.26, $A = \{b\}$, then A is ψg^{\wedge} -closed but not $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ -closed set

In Example 3.26, $A = \{a,d\}$, then A is sag^* closed but not $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed set

In Example 3.26, $A = \{a,d\}$, then A is gp - closed. but not $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed set

In Example 3.26, $A = \{a,d\}$, then A is g^*p - closed. but not $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed set

In Example 3.26, $A = \{a,b\}$, then A is $r^{\wedge}g$ closed but not $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed set

Remark 3.29: $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed sets and g - closed sets are independent to each other as seen from the following examples.

Example 3.30:

* Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}, \tau = \{X, \phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a,b,c\}\}$ Let $A = \{c\}$, then A is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed but not g - closed.

* Let $X = \{a, b, c,d\}, \tau = \{X, \phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a,b,c\}\}$. Let $A = \{a, b, d\}$ then A is g -closed but not an $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed set.

Remark 3.31: $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed sets and g^* -closed sets are independent to each other as seen from the following example.

Example 3.32:

* Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}, \tau = \{X, \phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a,b,c\}\}$ Let $A = \{c\}$, then A is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed but not g^* - closed.

* Let $X = \{a, b, c,d\}, \tau = \{X, \phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a,b,c\}\}$. Let $A = \{a, b, d\}$ then A is g^* -closed but not an $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed set.

Remark 3.33: $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed sets and $\alpha^{\wedge}g$ - closed sets are independent to each other as seen from the following examples.

Example 3.34:

Let $X = \{a, b, c,d\}, \tau = \{X, \phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a,b,c\}\}$. Let $A = \{c\}$, then A is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed but not an $\alpha^{\wedge}g$ closed set in X and the subset $\{a,b,d\}$ is an $\alpha^{\wedge}g$ closed set but not $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed in X .

Remark 3.35: The above discussions are shown in the following diagram.

1

Theorem 3.36: Let A be an $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed set in a topological space X . Then $\alpha cl(A) - A$ contains no non-empty αg -closed set in X .

Proof: Let F be a α -closed set such that $F \subset \alpha cl(A) - A$. Then $F \subset X - A$ implies $A \subset X - F$. Since A is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed and $X - F$ is α -open, then $gcl(A) \subset X - F$. That is $F \subset X - \alpha cl(A)$. Hence $F \subset \alpha cl(A) \cap (X - \alpha cl(A)) = \emptyset$. Thus $F = \emptyset$, whence $\alpha cl(A) - A$ does not contain nonempty αg -closed set.

Remark 3.37: The converse of the above theorem need not be true, that means if $\alpha cl(A) - A$ contains no

nonempty αg -closed set, then A need not to be an $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed as seen in the following example.

Example 3.38:

Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}, \tau = \{X, \phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}\}$. Let $A = \{b\}$. $gcl(A) - A = \{d\}$, it does not contain non-empty αg -closed set in X . But $A = \{b\}$ is not an $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed set.

Theorem 3.39: The finite union of two αg closed sets are $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed.

Proof: Assume that A and B are $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed sets in X . Let $A \cup B \subset U$ where U is αg -open. Then $A \subset U$ and $B \subset U$. Since A and B are $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed, $\alpha cl(A) \subset U$ and $\alpha cl(B) \subset U$. Then $\alpha cl(A \cup B) = \alpha cl(A) \cup \alpha cl(B) \subset U$. Hence $A \cup B$ is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed.

Remark 3.40: The intersection of two $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed set in X need not be an $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed set.

Theorem 3.41: If A is an $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed subset of X such that $A \subset B \subset \alpha cl(A)$, then B is an $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed set.

Proof: Let $B \subset U$ where U is αg -open. Then $A \subset B$ implies $A \subset U$. Since A is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed, $\alpha cl(A) \subset U$. By hypothesis $\alpha cl(B) \subset \alpha cl(\alpha cl(A)) = \alpha cl(A) \subset U$. Hence B is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed.

Remark 3.42: The converse of the above theorem need not be true as seen in the following example.

Example 3.43:

Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}, \tau = \{X, \phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}\}$. Let $A = \{d\}$ and $B = \{c, d\}$. Then A and B are $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed sets. But $A \subset B$ is not a subset of $\alpha cl(A)$.

4. Alpha Alpha of Generalized Star Open Set:

Definition 4.1: A set $A \subset X$ is called alpha alpha of generalized star open ($\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ open) set if and only if its compliment is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed. The collection of all $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ open sets is denoted by $\alpha(\alpha G)^* O(X)$.

5. $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ Continuous and $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ Irresolute Functions:

Definition 5.1: A function $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is called $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ continuous if every $f^{-1}(V)$ is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed in X for every closed set V of Y .

Definition 5.2: A function $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is called $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ irresolute if every $f^{-1}(V)$ is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed in X for every $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed set V of Y .

Example 5.3: Let $X = \{a, b, c\}, \tau = \{X, \phi, \{a\}, \{a, b\}\}$ and $Y = \{a, b, c\}$,

$\sigma = \{Y, \phi, \{a\}\}$. Define $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ by $f(a)=a, f(b)=b, f(c)=c$. Here the inverse image of the closed sets in Y are $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed sets in X . Hence f is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ continuous.

Example 5.4: Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}, \tau = \{\phi, X, \{a, b\}, \{c\}, \{a, b, c\}\}$ and $Y = X$,

$\sigma = \{Y, \phi, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}\}$.

Define $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ by $f(a)=a, f(b)=b, f(c)=c, f(d)=d$. The inverse image of every $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed set in Y is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed set in X . Hence f is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ irresolute.

Remark 5.5: Every $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ irresolute function is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ continuous but the converse is not true as seen in the following example.

Example 5.6: In example 5.3, f is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ continuous but not $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ irresolute.

Remark 5.7: Every continuous function is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ continuous. But the converse is not true as seen in the

following example.

Example 5.8:

Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$. $\tau = \{X, \phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}\}$ and $Y = X$,
 $\sigma = \{Y, \phi, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{a, c, d\}\}$. Define $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ the identity mapping. Then f is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ continuous but not continuous.

Theorem 5.9: Let $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ and $g : (Y, \sigma) \rightarrow (Z, \eta)$ be any two functions. Then

- (i) $(g \circ f)$ is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ -continuous if g is continuous and f is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ -continuous
- (ii) $(g \circ f)$ is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ -irresolute, if g is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ -irresolute and f is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ -irresolute.
- (iii) $(g \circ f)$ is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ continuous if g is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ -continuous and f is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ -irresolute.

Proof:

(i) Let V be any closed set in (Z, η) . Then $f^{-1}(V)$ is closed in (Y, σ) , since g is continuous. By hypothesis $f^{-1}(g^{-1}(V))$ is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed in (X, τ) . Hence $g \circ f$ is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ continuous.

(ii) Let V be $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed set in (Z, η) . Since g is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ irresolute, $g^{-1}(V)$ is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed in (Y, σ) . As f is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ irresolute, $f^{-1}(g^{-1}(V)) = (g \circ f)^{-1}(V)$ is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed in (X, τ) . Hence $g \circ f$ is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ irresolute.

(iii) Let V be closed in (Z, η) . Since g is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ continuous, $g^{-1}(V)$ is α -closed in (Y, σ) . As f is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ irresolute, $f^{-1}(g^{-1}(V)) = (g \circ f)^{-1}(V)$ is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ closed in (X, τ) . Hence $(g \circ f)$ is $\alpha(\alpha g)^*$ continuous.

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